

THE HUMAN NERVOUS SYSTEM

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Abstract: *The human nervous system has a very complex structure. Scientists are still studying the nervous system, especially the brain, and will continue to do so. Figuratively speaking, the brain is the most studied and the brain is the least studied! In this book, I will cover various aspects of the nervous system and psyche. I would like to give you a brief overview of the structure of the nervous system so that they can be understood by students.*

The brain consists of two hemispheres, the right and left hemispheres. In the left hemisphere of the brain are the centers of speech. Therefore, in the left hemisphere of the brain, all speech-related thinking operations are performed. The right hemisphere of the brain is responsible for analyzing the spatial location of objects. For example, it analyzes the appearance of surrounding houses, trees, cars, statues, and objects of any shape.

This means that the right hemisphere of the brain perceives the world without words, and the visual analyzer is important here. The left hemisphere perceives information expressed in words. Figuratively speaking, the left hemisphere perceives the world mainly with words and the right hemisphere with the eyes. When this harmony is maintained, a person's memory is strengthened.

The right hemisphere is also responsible for capturing the geometric shapes you see in books. However, if you need to verbalize any spatial object or geometric shape, the left hemisphere will help. So the left hemisphere has a tongue. But for now, the information I have provided is specific to some of them. In the left hemisphere, the speech centers are located in the right hemisphere of the brain. This means that most of the functions performed by the left hemisphere in the left hemisphere are assigned to the right hemisphere. There are also ambidexters, meaning that both hemispheres of the brain are involved in the performance of higher mental functions. They can do the same thing with both hands. However,

this does not mean that he can write with both hands. For example, an ambidexter uses his pen in his right hand when writing and uses his left hand when cutting bread. "Clean" squirrels are around 10-15%. There are a lot of ambidexters and idiots among us. In the abyss, both hemispheres of the brain are involved in performing the function of speech. Therefore, if speech is impaired due to a stroke in the ambidexter, it recovers quickly.

How does the nervous system control the internal organs?

There are no organs or tissues in the body without the involvement of the nervous system. That is why there is a saying among the people that "all diseases are caused by nerves." There is a lot of meaning behind it. The nervous system controls and controls all the activities of the body. No process can take place without the involvement of the nervous system. Various functions, such as tearing, salivation, vascular bleeding, sweating, and urination, are directly involved and controlled by the nervous system.

The part of the nervous system that controls the activity of the internal organs is called the autonomic nervous system. The autonomic nervous system is divided into sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems. Together, they manage the activities of the internal organs.

What is a neuron?

A nerve cell is called a neuron. Just as all the organs are made up of cells, so is the nervous system made up of cells. These cells are neurons. The cortex of the cerebral hemispheres contains 14 billion cells. there is a cell, a neuron. Neurons have different structures. The body of the neuron is gray, and the fibers that come out of it are white. One long fiber of a neuron is called an axon. Through the axon, impulses are transmitted from the neuron's body to other neurons and tissues. A number of other growths in neurons are called dendrites.

Dendrites are fibers that carry impulses to a neuron. The cerebral cortex is gray. The cortex contains the centers that control all human activity. These are the centers of movement, intuition, speech, sight, hearing, smell, and taste. They are also referred to as analyzers. Unlike other neurons, cortical neurons have a mind! I mean, they are involved not only in movement and intuition, but also in mental activity. Therefore, when a person's brain is damaged, mental activity is also impaired. Damage to the spinal cord or peripheral nerves does not change mental function.

What is an analyzer?

An analyzer is a nerve structure that receives, processes, and responds to external information. In the nervous system, vision, hearing, taste, smell, general perception, movement, and speech analyzers are different.

The center of the analyzer is located in different areas of the cerebral cortex. For example, the visual analyzer is located in the neck, the auditory analyzer in the temples, the motion analyzer in the forehead, the sensory analyzer in the upper part, and the speech analyzers in the temples and forehead. If the speech analyzer is damaged, speech is impaired, if the motion analyzer is damaged, paralysis develops, if the hearing analyzer is damaged, the person becomes deaf, and so on.

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